

Graph-Based Defense Strategies for CAN Bus Security: A Comprehensive Review

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Abstract. Modern automotive systems heavily rely on the Controller Area Network (CAN) protocol. This standard protocol enables communication between multiple Electronic Control Units (ECUs) that manage critical vehicle functions such as acceleration, braking, and steering. However, CANs lack fundamental security mechanisms, and as automotive technology evolves with increasingly intelligent vehicles offering innovative applications through ECUs, the growing number of ECUs creates more attack surfaces, making the CAN bus more vulnerable to cyber-attacks. This paper offers a detailed overview of the security issues and vulnerabilities of CAN bus systems, the available datasets for CAN bus research, and the existing graph-based defense techniques for intrusion detection. In addition, this article compares these techniques and highlights open issues and future directions.

Keywords: CAN security · Graph-based defense strategies · CAN bus vulnerabilities · Intrusion detection systems · Automotive cybersecurity · CAN bus datasets · Vehicular network security.

1 Introduction

As the most widely used form of transportation in human life, automobile safety has long been considered a top priority [56]. The automotive industry is rapidly evolving, with modern automobiles emerging as complex cyber-physical machines [28]. Modern vehicles are becoming more sophisticated and functional. Advancements in technology make them smarter and more user-friendly than in earlier generations. In 1980, vehicles contained only 1% electronic components, but today that figure has increased to 50%, which will continue to increase with the beginning of autonomous cars that will depend on powerful computer systems, sensors, networking and satellite navigation, all of which are based on electronics [43].

In automobiles, ECUs are embedded devices that transmit information and instructions through the vehicle's internal network [48]. The CAN bus is the

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most popular communication technology in cars, making communication easier [56]. When the CAN bus was designed in the 1980s, it was a secure system insulated from the outside world, prioritizing reliability and error handling. CAN bus performs well with a faster data transmission rate and as a reliable and error-free system due to its immunity to electrical interference and error correction capability [28]. However, despite these features, CAN lacks encryption and authentication mechanisms, making modern cars easy targets for intruders and exposing the system to potential internal and external threats [48]. Security researchers have shown that modern automobiles can be attacked by compromising the CAN bus, often through access to the OBD-II port, over-the-air (OTA) updates, or communication channels such as Bluetooth, Wi-Fi, and cellular networks [36]. For example, a hacker can hack into the ECU and activate several vehicle systems such as braking, turning on the windshield wipers, activating the locking mechanism, turning off the light, and changing the vehicle’s speedometer and other critical components. In [34], the authors exploited the head unit (radio) to gain remote access, resulting in physical control of the 2014 Jeep Cherokee model [42]. Such scenarios can result in dangerous situations on the road, such as the engine stalling while the vehicle is in motion or the brakes failing, which could cause an accident [48].

In response to these attacks, recent years have seen significant advances in the development of intrusion detection systems (IDSs) [24, 4]. IDS refers to an electronic system that functions as an additional ECU integrated into the vehicle network to detect or predict potential attacks, protecting against intruders while maintaining communication performance without adding additional overhead [45, 6]. Recently, IDSs based on Machine Learning (ML) have become popular due to their promising accuracy, performance, and ability to detect complex patterns [43].

The structure and semantics of the CAN data are proprietary and not openly accessible, as they are considered confidential by vehicle manufacturers and stored in a file known as the CAN data base. This confidentiality makes the development of IDSs for widespread adoption challenging, and achieving full accuracy against certain attacks is unrealistic. However, IDSs that utilize the CAN ID field can still effectively detect attacks as a generalized solution, depending on the feature selection [52]. Graph-based ML utilizes graphs and their properties to identify patterns that can be used to create a generalized IDS for all types of cyberattacks [13, 54]. This paper analyzes the security issues and vulnerabilities of intelligent vehicles, discusses existing graph-based defense techniques, highlights open problems, and provides a perspective on future directions.

2 Overview of CAN Bus Technology

The rise of connected cars has increased the number of advanced sensors and chips, causing challenges such as reduced communication reliability due to complex wiring and diverse components from different manufacturers [49]. To address this, BOSCH developed the widely used CAN protocol, which enables ECU

communication through a message broadcast bus system with multiple masters. Fig. 1 shows the overview of a CAN bus in a vehicle.

Fig. 1. Overview of a CAN interface

The ECUs on a CAN bus within a vehicle exchange information via the communication bus, where each ECU can see the messages simultaneously. All ECUs are connected to the bus using twisted pairs of cables, which are CAN high and CAN low. Twisting both wires tightly ensures uniform electromagnetic interference, minimizing errors [47]. The speed of the CAN protocol ranges from 125kbit/s to 1Mbit/s [45]. Fig. 2 represents a CAN frame in the standard format.

SOF	ID	Control	DLC	Data	CRC	ACK	EOF
Start of Frame	Arbitration Identifier	Control	Data Length Code	Data	Cyclic Redundancy Checksum	Acknowledge	End of Frame
1-Bit	11-Bits	3-Bits	4-Bits	0-8 Bytes	16-Bits	2-Bits	7-Bits

Fig. 2. CAN protocol frame format

A CAN message begins with a 1-bit Start of Frame (SOF) field, signaling all ECUs that a message is about to begin. The CAN Identifier (CAN ID) field, which contains 11 bits for standard format or 29 bits for an extended frame, defines the message’s content and priority. The control field includes a Data Length Code (DLC) that specifies the number of bytes in the payload, followed by the payload itself, which can be up to 64 bits or 8 bytes of data. CAN bus has an error handling mechanism. The Cyclic Redundancy Check (CRC) field holds the data checksum for error detection, whereas the ACK field confirms the

successful transmission by the receiver. Finally, the end-of-frame (EOF) field marks the end of the message [43].

When multiple ECUs need to send CAN messages simultaneously, their IDs determine which one wins the transmission right. The message with the highest priority, indicated by the lowest ID value, is transmitted; for example, 0x0000 is the lowest ID value on a CAN bus. ECUs responsible for critical functions, such as acceleration and braking systems, typically have higher priority in accessing the bus [43].

3 SECURITY ISSUES AND VULNERABILITIES OF CAN BUS SYSTEMS

3.1 Security Issues

The CAN bus uses a broadcast mechanism for message exchange; Any ECU can send a message to the CAN bus at any time, which can then be received by all other ECUs connected to the bus. However, the CAN protocol lacks inbuilt authentication and encryption mechanisms [10], which means that CAN messages do not include information about their senders or receivers. This vulnerability can be exploited by an attacker who gains access to network traffic, posing a significant cybersecurity risk to the system.

3.2 Potential Attacks

The CAN bus is primarily vulnerable to three types of attacks: injection (fabrication), suspension, and masquerade (impersonation) attacks [44].

Injection Attack: In an injection attack, the attacker exploits vulnerabilities in the CAN bus system to inject fabricated or manipulated messages. Some common injection attacks include DoS, Fuzzing, Spoofing, and Replay attacks.

- (a) **DoS attacks:** DoS attacks try to make communication services unavailable by flooding the CAN bus with high-priority frames, preventing other ECUs from sending lower-priority frames. This can introduce delays in sending frames from high-priority CAN IDs, which have the potential to induce unexpected behavior in the vehicle.
- (b) **Fuzzing attacks:** In a fuzzing attack, the attacker generates frames with random values for CAN IDs, DLCs, and payloads, then floods the network, overwhelming legitimate frames with this randomized traffic. There are two approaches in fuzzing attacks: using valid CAN IDs that exist in normal traffic and using entirely random CAN IDs.
- (c) **Spoofing attacks:** A spoofing attack requires an initial payload analysis for at least one specific CAN ID. The attacker uses this information to inject altered payloads targeting that CAN ID. Since the CAN ID appears legitimate, other ECUs may respond to malicious data assuming that it is valid [58].

- (d) **Replay attacks:** In replay attacks, attackers intercept and store legitimate CAN frames by observing network traffic. These stored frames are then re-transmitted at different times, potentially causing inconsistencies in the system. For example, previously recorded speedometer readings might be sent again, leading to misinformation on the vehicle dashboard.

Suspension Attack: In a suspension attack, the attacker aims to disrupt frame transmission from a target ECU for a specified period by exploiting the error handling mechanisms of the CAN protocol or deploying malicious software. A suspension attack can turn into a black hole attack if it stops an ECU that serves as a bridge between two or more subnets, blocking communication in the network [11]. The ability to detect such attacks can vary based on the targeted CAN IDs and the duration of suspension.

Masquerade Attack: In a masquerade attack, the attacker observes and analyzes the CAN IDs of the messages and the transmission frequencies of a specific ECU [35]. The attack is performed by suspending the ECU's transmission and sending spoofed frames that mimic the same CAN ID, DLC, payload characteristics, and timing, thereby keeping CAN traffic unchanged. For example, an attacker might monitor ECU B, stop it from transmitting, and then use another ECU A to send a fabricated message replicating ECU B's transmissions [44].

Detecting spoofing and replay attacks can be more difficult than DoS and fuzzing attacks, as these attacks involve less frequent injections. Furthermore, carrying out a masquerade attack requires advanced hacking skills and a thorough understanding of the vehicle [53].

3.3 Attack Surfaces

An attacker must connect to the CAN bus to execute attacks, either through direct access, such as using the On-Board Diagnostic (OBD-II) port while the vehicle is parked, or via remote access [36]. Numerous remote access technologies are widely used in vehicle-to-vehicle and vehicle-to-infrastructure communications and serve as potential attack surfaces. Common examples include anti-theft systems, tire pressure monitoring systems (TPMS), remote keyless entry, Bluetooth, radio systems, Wi-Fi, cellular networks, satellite communication, and telematics units [26]. Additionally, due to the advancement in automotive technology and the increase in autonomous vehicles, vehicular sensors such as ultrasonic sensors, radar, lidar, Global Positioning Systems (GPS), and cameras are becoming common and can also be exploited [14, 16, 25, 43].

For example, an attacker can use spoofed GPS information that provides vehicle location and time, or use CAN messages to uncover driving routes, posing a significant threat to driver privacy [30]. This may lead to the exposure of personal profiles and real-world privacy breaches. Bluetooth vulnerabilities include memory exploits that allow a paired device to execute malicious code, potentially

compromising the vehicle’s engine systems. Although there are secure protocols, they are often not implemented in commercial systems due to inefficiency. Furthermore, automotive manufacturers frequently connect infotainment systems - the main attack surfaces - to safety-critical components to improve functionality [50], a vulnerability exploited in the 2015 Chrysler Jeep hack by Miller and Valasek [34].

4 AVAILABLE DATASETS FOR CAN BUS RESEARCH

There are several publicly available CAN datasets with attack data, as discussed below.

Hacking and Countermeasure Research Lab (HCRL) has four datasets available for academic use, which are the Car Hacking Data Set for Intrusion Detection (HCRL-CH) [17], CAN Data Set for Intrusion Detection (HCRL-OTIDS) [29, 2], Survival analysis data set for automobile IDS (HCRL-SA) [3], and Car Hacking Attack and Defense Challenge (HCRL-CHDC) [1]. The HCRL-CH dataset contains 500 seconds of benign data and four attack datasets (DoS, fuzzing, and two spoofing attacks) that can be easily detected due to significant frequency changes. Although benign data was collected during driving, signal decoding revealed that the car was stationary during attack data collection [53], additionally benign and attack data are stored in different file formats. The HCRL-OTIDS dataset, collected from a KIA Soul, includes benign data and DoS, fuzzing, and masquerade attack data. Although it is the only data set that features remote frames and responses with data from a moving vehicle [13] it lacks labeled ground truth, limiting attack detection. HCRL-SA includes data from multiple vehicles (HYUNDAI YF Sonata, KIA Soul, and CHEVROLET Spark), with basic attacks that can be easily detected using frequency-based IDS, however benign data are limited. The HCRL-CHDC dataset, collected from a Hyundai Avante CN7 for a competition, includes benign and attack data in one file, in this dataset benign data are also limited [44].

SynCAN [31] which is published with CANet [18] and TU Eindhoven CAN bus intrusion dataset (TUECAN) [32] are two public datasets with synthetic attacks. SynCAN comprises 10 CAN IDs, each supporting up to four signals. It is used to train and evaluate unsupervised payload-based CAN Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) [38]. The attacks are categorized as plateau, continuous, playback, suppress, and flooding. In the TUECAN dataset, benign data was collected from two cars (Opel Astra and Renault Clio) and a prototype CAN bus, with synthetic attacks including diagnostic, fuzzing, replay, suspension, and DoS.

The real ORNL Automotive Dynamometer (ROAD) CAN intrusion dataset [53] consists of more than 3.5 hours of vehicle CAN data. In addition, it captures ambient data from various activities, featuring real and simulated attacks, including fuzzing, fabrication, stealth variants, and advanced masquerade techniques. Masquerade attack variants were created by removing legitimate messages during post-processing. Although labels are unavailable, attack IDs and

intervals are provided as metadata (in JSON format) to help identify attack messages. Attack data were collected while the vehicle operated solely on a dynamometer. This dataset is particularly recognized for model performance evaluations [5, 43].

The CAN-MIRGU dataset [44] is a newer publicly available CAN bus dataset with the largest recorded amount of normal and attack data. CAN-MIRGU features 36 attacks, including 26 real injection attacks and 10 simulated ones. This dataset has 56 CAN IDs and attacks target 13 CAN IDs. It has 17 hours of attack-free data. Real injection attacks last over 2 hours, suspension attacks for 26 minutes, and masquerade attacks for 19 minutes. Each CAN message in the dataset contains a timestamp, channel name, CAN ID, data field, message size, and label. The dataset covers major attack types [42, 44] currently available.

5 EXISTING GRAPH BASED DEFENSE TECHNIQUES

After an extensive search, only a few graph-based papers were found and selected based on their relevance to the research topic, innovative contributions, and publication in reputable journals or conferences. These articles, ensuring high quality, were published after 2020. A detailed description of the selected papers is provided in the following.

Islam et al. [22] first introduced a graph-based defense system for the CAN bus, constructing graphs from a window of 200 CAN messages. In this system, nodes represent CAN IDs, edges link sequential CAN IDs, the cycle indicates a loop between sequential CAN IDs, and the first CAN message of the window serves as the graph's root. Using the chi-square metric to compare successive graphs, their method achieved a misclassification rate of 5.26% for DoS, 10% for fuzzy attacks, 4.76% for replay attacks and none for spoofing, outperforming ID sequence-based methods by up to 13.73%. Despite its accuracy and applicability without modifying the CAN protocol, the approach is computationally intensive for large datasets due to the need to compare all attack-free graph populations with the graph population under test. This paper does not consider the mixed attacks which has been introduced by other researchers [13, 54, 21]. Furthermore, the data set [17] has limitations as attack data is collected from a stationary vehicle, reducing confidence in results and threatening validity [23].

Jedh et al. [23] proposed a similar graph-based approach to detect message injection attacks. They used a window of 100 CAN message sequences to generate a directed graph and extracted two features: cosine and Pearson correlation similarities. Then three techniques were used for attack detection: threshold-based, LSTM-RNN, and Change Point Detection (CPD). The model was evaluated using a real dataset [9] from a 2017 Ford Transit 500 vehicle in motion, enhanced by artificially generated messages related to RPM (revolutions per minute) and speed [7]. The evaluations showed a detection accuracy of 98.45% with LSTM-RNN and 97.32% with the threshold method. However, this research

Table 1. Comparative overview of graph-based CAN bus intrusion detection studies in recent years

Study	Dataset	Features	Technique
Jedh et al. [23] (2021)	2017 Ford Transit 500 vehicle dataset [9]	Cosine and Pearson correlation similarities	LSTM-RNN & Threshold method
Islam et al. [21] (2022)	HCRL-OTIDS [2]	Indegree, outdegree, and PageRank	GGNB
Xiao et al. [57] (2023)	HCRL-CH [17] and HCRL-OTIDS [2]	IDs & Payload	CAN-GAT & CAN-GAT-2
Zhang et al. [59] (2023)	CSET [39], Moving vehicle [23], and Ford Transit 500 vehicle [9] dataset	Payload and ID pair frequency	GNN & Federated learning
Marfo et al. [33] (2024)	ROAD dataset [53]	Statistical attributes (mean and standard deviation)	Random forest and XGBoost classifiers
Walid et al. [54] (2024)	OpelAstra dataset [15]	PageRank, CC, BC, IDC, and ODC	GaussianNB, MultinomialNB, ComplementNB, LDA, DT, Gradient Boosting, and XGBoost

only addresses message injection attacks, and the dataset used is comparatively small.

In another paper [21], the authors constructed graphs similar to those discussed in previous research. They utilized graph properties such as indegree and outdegree, along with PageRank, as features to develop a Gaussian naive Bayes (GGNB)-based intrusion detection system (IDS). This system was validated using the HCRL-OTIDS dataset, achieving high accuracy in detecting denial of service (DoS), fuzzy, spoofing, replay, and mixed attacks. Furthermore, GGNB requires significantly less training and testing time than an SVM-based classifier [51]. However, it does not include suspension and masquerade attacks, nor does it address unknown attacks.

To balance computational complexity and capture association, Xiao et al. [57] constructed a graph using 50 CAN bus message frames, with each node (CAN ID is represented as a node) connected to a maximum of 10 adjacent nodes (5 before and 5 after). This study used HCRL-CH and HCRL-OTIDS datasets and used the payload field of CAN bus messages, including IDs, to capture correlations between traffic bytes and improve detection accuracy and efficiency. Each node has a feature, an 8-byte vector representing the payload field, padded with zeros if the payload field is less than 8. This approach optimizes computational cost while preserving the temporal relationships between messages. This research proposes the control area network graph attention networks (CAN-GAT) model,

which enhances feature extraction by adding learnable weights and dot multiplication, leading to faster convergence and better performance than the GAT-based model. The CAN-GAT-2 model, based on a two-layer structure, achieves even better performance.

Devnath et al. [13] present a novel Graph Convolutional Network (GCN)-based intrusion detection system for CAN bus security utilizing the HCRL-OTIDS dataset. The window-based graph construction outperformed state-of-the-art IDS models by achieving superior accuracy, precision, and recall with minimal feature engineering by employing only two graph-based features: maximum indegree, and maximum outdegree. This method is particularly effective in detecting mixed injection attacks (DoS, Fuzzy, Spoofing, and Replay) attacks; however, the dataset used in this study excludes masquerade attacks, and the attack durations are relatively short. Additional validation is required using the latest and larger datasets.

Park et al. [41] propose G-IDCS, a window-based graph intrusion detection system for the CAN bus, trained on the HCRL-CHDC dataset. The system reduces the detection message overhead by a factor of 30 while improving the accuracy by 9%. G-IDCS employs a combination of a threshold-based IDS and an ML classifier to effectively identify attack types. Three key features are extracted from the constructed graph and used in both classifiers: elapsed time, maximum degree, and number of edges. The threshold values for the threshold-based IDS values are calculated using normal CAN data. For the ML classifier, a random forest is utilized that is trained on labeled normal and attack data. Various thresholding techniques are applied, like max-min thresholds, Z-scores $|z| = 3$, and Tukey’s method ($3 \times \text{IQR}$ distance) and all demonstrated high validation performance. Although G-IDCS offers excellent performance across both models and provides some level of interpretability by identifying features used in attack detection through threshold-based IDS, it does not explicitly integrate well-established Explainable AI (XAI) techniques or provide any interpretation of their prediction outcome. Moreover, its dataset lacks coverage of suspension and masquerade attacks, and the durations of the attacks are relatively brief.

Zhang et al. [59] propose a Graph Neural Network (GNN) using window-based directed graphs as a CAN bus anomaly detection system that can detect attacks in as short as 3 milliseconds (ms). The node attributes denote the CAN message data, while the edge attributes represent the frequency of the CAN ID pair. The datasets used include the can Sign extraction and translation (CSET) data set [39], a moving vehicle data set [23], and a data set collected on a Ford Transit 500 [40]. A two-stage classifier for CAN intrusion detection is proposed where the first-stage GNN uses a one-class classification layer to detect anomalies, while the second-stage classifier with an openmax layer identifies specific attack types. In addition, federated learning is employed to train a universal model that covers a wide range of driving scenarios, vehicle states, and driving behaviors that increase generalizability while preserving privacy. The presented IDS achieves performance comparable to that of content-based and statistical

IDSs. However, federated learning poses security risks, as malicious participants can inject poisoning data to degrade model performance.

Marfo et al. [33] present a framework to detect masquerade attacks on the CAN bus using graph machine learning. This approach constructs window-based graphs while also considering an offset factor. Instead of simply starting each new window after the full size of the previous one, it uses an offset factor that represents the number of samples that separate consecutive windows. This ensures no data loss and allows the model to capture communication patterns that may span multiple windows. To enhance detection capabilities, the method incorporates statistical attributes (mean and standard deviation) derived from time series data as node features. By integrating these time-series features with graph embeddings, the approach improves AUC-ROC values [19] across various attacks (fabrication, suspension, and masquerade attacks) using time-based windows. The experimental results on the ROAD dataset [53] indicate significant improvements over baselines with graph only, validated by statistical analysis. Experiments were conducted using Random Forest (RF) and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) classifiers, but RF was selected because of its simpler interpretability and less intensive hyperparameter tuning process. Although this study improves detection capabilities, it focuses primarily on masquerade attacks. The offset factor increases complexity compared to other window-based methods. Further optimization is required for real-time implementation in resource-constrained vehicular environments, and the approach needs to be validated on recent datasets.

Walid et al. [54] use a graph-based approach to develop an intrusion detection system. The features used include PageRank, closeness centrality (CC), betweenness centrality (BC), in-degree centrality (IDC), and out-degree centrality (ODC). This study utilizes the OpelAstra dataset [15] and applies the GGNB, Multinomial Naive Bayes (MultinomialNB), Complement Naive Bayes (ComplementNB), Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), Decision Tree (DT), Gradient Boosting, and XGBoost models. It demonstrates that using just 30% of the available 70% training data (21% of the total dataset) achieves high accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score while reducing training time by more than 2.3 times compared to the full dataset. This paper focuses solely on comparing the training times for DoS attack detection.

Table 1 presents a comparative overview of the graph-based CAN bus intrusion detection studies mentioned above.

6 OPEN ISSUES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Despite considerable progress in CAN bus intrusion detection, particularly with graph-based approaches, several issues remain unresolved, and opportunities exist for further research and development. This section highlights key open issues and future research directions for improving CAN bus security.

CAN bus offers reduced costs, built-in error detection, higher speed, and flexibility, and is widely used in various industries, including aircraft, railways,

and X-ray machines, together with the automotive industry [46, 37]. However, it still has weaknesses and leaves room for improvement[12]. There is a need for higher-bandwidth communication systems due to the increasing demand for data exchange for modern technologies like Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS). Even with a space-saving bus topology, more sensors and actuators increase the complexity of the cable and add weights (60 to 100 kg) equivalent to an additional passenger [27]. CAN bus has time delays, short message lengths, and a delay for messages with a high identifier. The first question that comes to mind is, if the CAN bus has limitations, then are there any better alternatives to it? For example, a bus system with Optical Networks [27] or an improved and security-enabled Controller Area Network with Flexible Data-Rate (CAN FD). CAN FD is a newer technology that provides a high bandwidth of up to 8 Mbps and a payload of up to 64 Bytes [8].

Most of the reviewed studies use standard ML metrics only, including accuracy, precision, and recall, but False positive rate (FPR) and false negative rate (FNR) are critical IDS metrics in vehicles [55], especially in real-time driving, where incorrect alerts or missed threats can cause distractions, panic, or accidents.

Most solutions ignore placement and deployment strategies and lack details on post-deployment update mechanisms. Only one study explored a universal model for various attack scenarios, and while a few addressed unknown attacks, none attempted to classify their root causes where they originated, and what triggered them. Furthermore, there is no specific benchmark for the created IDS, thus comparison between solutions is difficult, and there is a need for real-world proof to establish the impact and validity of the solution [4].

Real-world complexity (computations, memory, etc.) and cost of maintenance analysis are not addressed in most of the studies. There is no mention of how to mitigate damage during an attack scenario. For example, after intrusion detection, it remains unclear how vehicles can relay information to other entities if connected to the VANET (Vehicular Ad hoc Network), such as nearby vehicles, pedestrians, barriers, or infrastructure, or use satellite communication to alert others about the threat [20].

The decisions made by the IDS lack clear interpretation, limiting trust and transparency. XAI methods like SHapley Additive Explanations (SHAP) can help analyze individual predictions to reveal patterns behind complex black-box models.

Future research can explore the pros and cons of CAN and its alternatives while addressing key IDS challenges, including deployment strategies, update mechanisms, root cause analysis, benchmarking, real-world validation, system constraints, attack mitigation through VANET, and improved transparency through XAI techniques like SHAP.

7 CONCLUSION

The CAN bus protocol is widely adopted in modern vehicles despite its inherent lack of security mechanisms. This paper highlights the progress of graph-based methods in addressing the security challenges and vulnerabilities of the CAN bus protocol. The examined studies show the effectiveness of graph representations in capturing CAN bus traffic patterns and detecting various attack types with high accuracy. Techniques such as graph neural networks, federated learning, and hybrid approaches have proven effective in enhancing detection capabilities while improving computational efficiency. However, the review also reveals persistent challenges, including the lack of real-world deployment strategies, limited coverage of attack scenarios, and insufficient attention to explainability and user trust. Future research should address these gaps by exploring alternatives such as CAN FD and Optical Networks as an alternative to the CAN bus, developing standard benchmark datasets for better solution comparison, and incorporating XAI techniques like SHAP for greater transparency and trust. Furthermore, real-world validation, attack mitigation strategies, and the development of universal and adaptive IDS models remain critical areas for investigation. By addressing these open issues, the research community can further advance the security and reliability of CAN bus systems or lean toward a better communication protocol, ensuring safer and more robust vehicular networks in the era of connected and autonomous vehicles.

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